

Empowering Nepalese Community through ICT: Opportunity, Implementation, and Challenges

Introduction

In the modern era of technological advancements, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has emerged as a powerful tool for empowering communities around the world. In the context of Nepal, ICT presents a unique opportunity to uplift and strengthen the Nepalese community through increased access to information, connectivity, and educational resources. This article delves into the various opportunities, implementation strategies, and challenges associated with harnessing ICT for community empowerment in Nepal. Opportunities for empowering the Nepalese community through ICT are ample and transformative. One key opportunity lies in the access to information and resources that ICT provides. With the propagation of smartphones and the internet, individuals in Nepal can now easily obtain valuable information on a wide range of topics, from healthcare to agriculture practices. Furthermore, the increased connectivity through the internet and mobile technology has facilitated communication and collaboration among community members, enabling the sharing of knowledge and ideas across geographical boundaries. Additionally, the availability of online educational resources and training programs has opened up new avenues for skill development and learning, thereby empowering individuals to enhance their capabilities and pursue economic opportunities.

The implementation of ICT initiatives in Nepal has been steadily gaining momentum, driven by both government efforts and private sector interventions (Kharel, 2018). The government has launched various initiatives to promote digital literacy and ICT infrastructure development across the country. For instance, the Digital Nepal Framework aims to create a digitally inclusive society by expanding access to ICT services and promoting digital skills training. Furthermore, the integration of ICT in public services and governance systems has enhanced transparency, efficiency, and citizen engagement. Through initiatives like e-governance platforms and online service delivery, the government is streamlining processes and improving service delivery to the Nepalese community (Sharma, 2001; Thapa, & Sæbø, 2012).

Government Initiatives

Nepal's National ICT Policy aims to integrate ICT across all sectors to foster sustainable development.

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Key objectives include enhancing digital literacy and infrastructure, promoting e-governance, encouraging private sector investment, and bridging the digital divide by ensuring ICT access in rural areas 2015. The Government of Nepal introduced the "Digital Nepal Framework" aiming to transform the country through digital innovation across various sectors including agriculture, health, education, energy, and tourism 2019. The government launched the "Digital Nepal Campaign," which aims to harness ICT for socio-economic transformation. Telecommunications Act (1997) provides the legal framework for developing and regulating telecommunications services in Nepal. It includes provisions for licensing and regulation of service providers, promoting fair competition, protecting consumer rights, and rules for infrastructure sharing and interconnection (Government of Nepal, 1997). The Electronic Transaction Act (ETA) (2008) regulates electronic transactions and cyber activities in Nepal. It includes legal recognition of electronic records and digital signatures, a framework for e-commerce, cybercrime prevention measures, and data protection and privacy guidelines. The Information Technology Policy (2015) aims to foster IT sector growth by focusing on IT infrastructure development, ICT education for human resource development, promotion of IT-enabled services (ITES) and Business Process Outsourcing (BPO), and encouragement of research and development in ICT Government of Nepal (Ministry of Information and Communications., 2015). The Broadband Policy (2015) aims to expand high-speed internet access across Nepal. Its objectives include ensuring affordable and reliable broadband services, enhancing broadband penetration in rural and underserved areas, and supporting e-learning, telemedicine, and e-governance services.

The National Cyber Security Policy (2016) aims to protect Nepal's information infrastructure by establishing a national cyber security framework, promoting awareness and capacity building, developing incident response mechanisms, and encouraging public-private partnerships for cyber security initiatives. The

Nepal Telecommunications Authority (NTA) oversees the telecommunications sector, issuing licences to operators, ensuring regulatory compliance, monitoring service quality, and promoting competition and consumer protection. The Digital Nepal Framework (2019) aims to transform Nepal into a digital economy by focusing on digital government and infrastructure, digital skills and innovation, and digital advancements in health, agriculture, energy, industry, and business. The National Broadband Policy (2022) aims to ensure high-speed broadband access for all citizens, especially in underserved and rural areas. Its objectives include expanding broadband infrastructure, making internet services more affordable, promoting broadband use in education, healthcare, and government services, and encouraging public-private partnerships to enhance broadband. The E-Government Master Plan (2021-2025) aims to enhance government transparency and efficiency through ICT by creating a unified e-government platform, implementing electronic procurement systems, enhancing data sharing among agencies, and promoting citizen engagement via digital platforms. The National Artificial Intelligence (AI) Policy (2023) seeks to promote AI development and application in public services, encourage AI research, establish ethical guidelines, and foster private sector investment in AI technologies. The Startup Ecosystem Development Program (2022) aims to nurture digital entrepreneurship in Nepal's ICT sector through financial incentives, grants, and support for startups (Islam, & Brody, 2024). It includes establishing incubation centers, innovation hubs, and offering training and mentorship programs for entrepreneurs. Additionally, the program focuses on creating a conducive regulatory environment to foster startup growth and innovation. The Data Protection and Privacy Act (2022) establishes a legal framework in Nepal to safeguard personal data. It defines individuals' rights over their data, sets guidelines for data collection, storage, and processing, mandates data breach notifications, and imposes penalties for non-compliance. The act emphasizes robust security measures to protect sensitive data from unauthorized access or misuse (Government of Nepal, 2022).

Current Position of Nepalese Society in ICT

Significant improvements have been made in telecommunication infrastructure. As of 2023, the teledensity in Nepal has surpassed 135%, indicating more than one connection per person on average. Efforts to expand broadband services have resulted in 72% internet penetration as of 2023, up from 44% in 2018 (Nepal Telecommunications Authority, 2023).

Fiber optic networks have expanded, and mobile broadband has seen substantial growth. Mobile phone penetration reached around 130% in 2023, from 89% in 2014, reflecting a significant increase in mobile device accessibility. The number of internet users in Nepal has grown substantially. From around 13 million users in 2014, the number has increased to over 22 million in 2023. The government has made strides in e-governance, providing various online services like e-passports, online tax filing, and digital payment systems for public services. The rise of digital payment systems, mobile banking, and ntech solutions has modernized the financial sector. As of 2023, over 70% of the adult population has access to digital banking services. There has been a push towards integrating ICT in education. Initiatives like the One Laptop Per Child Project and various e-learning platforms have been introduced to improve digital literacy among students. Numerous programs and training sessions have been conducted to enhance digital skills among the population, supported by both government and private sectors. Launched in 2009, eSewa has grown to become the leading digital wallet in Nepal, facilitating a wide range of services including bill payments, money transfers, and online shopping (International Telecommunication Union, 2023).

The state-owned telecom operator has played a crucial role in expanding 4G LTE services nationwide, significantly enhancing mobile internet speeds and accessibility. Projects like DHIS2 (District Health Information Software) have been implemented to improve health data management and service delivery. Mobile Penetration: 130% in 2023, up from 89% in 2014. Internet Penetration: 72% in 2023, up from 44% in 2018. Internet Users: Over 22 million in 2023, up from 13 million in 2014 (Thapa, 2023). Digital Banking Access: Over 70% of adults by 2023 (Internet World Stats, 2023; Nepal Rastra Bank, 2023; Nepal Telecom, 2023).

Implementation, Challenges, and Overcome

Implement telemedicine, Electronic Health Records (EHRs), and mobile health apps to enhance healthcare. Challenges include limited internet access, low digital literacy, and high ICT infrastructure costs. Overcome these by expanding internet and electricity access, training healthcare providers, and securing funding from various sources. Implement online marketing, booking platforms, and virtual tours to promote tourism in Nepal (Mishra, 2023). Challenges include poor internet connectivity, lack of digital skills among operators, and cyber security concerns.

Overcome these by improving internet infrastructure, offering digital skills training, and implementing robust cybersecurity measures. Implement digital marketplaces for direct sales, mobile apps for advisory services, and ICT tools for supply chain management in agriculture. Challenges include resistance to new technologies, limited smartphone and internet access, and the need for training programs (Sah, 2024). Overcome these by engaging farmer cooperatives, providing subsidies for smartphones and the internet, and organizing workshops for effective ICT use. Implement e-governance platforms for digital services like licensing and tax payments, online portals for citizen engagement, and digital identity systems. Challenges include inadequate ICT infrastructure, interoperability issues between government systems, and privacy concerns. Overcome these challenges by investing in ICT infrastructure, adopting standardized protocols for data sharing, and enforcing strong data protection regulations. Implement smart grid systems for energy optimization, use ICT tools for environmental monitoring, and deploy online education platforms for remote learning in sustainable development. Challenges include securing funding, coordinating stakeholders, and raising awareness. Overcome these by exploring diverse funding sources, establishing a central coordinating body, and conducting public awareness campaigns to emphasize the benefits of ICT in sustainability. Despite the promising opportunities, there are several challenges in implementing ICT for community empowerment in Nepal. Infrastructure limitations, particularly in rural areas, pose a significant barrier to ICT adoption and connectivity. Uneven access to electricity and internet connectivity further exacerbates the digital divide, hindering the full realization of ICT benefits for all segments of the Nepalese population. Moreover, the limited availability of affordable devices for accessing ICT resources remains a challenge, especially for low-income individuals who may not have the means to purchase smartphones or computers. Addressing these challenges will require a concerted effort from the government, private sector, and civil society to ensure that ICT truly empowers all members of the Nepalese community. Project-based dedicated performance in teaching and learning is the solution for the industry also (Mishra, 2023b).

Leveraging ICT for Empowering Nepalese Community

China's "Three Links and One Platform" initiative connected schools, teachers, and students via the Internet, improving educational access and reducing the urban-rural gap. India's National Digital Literacy

Mission and SWAYAM platform expanded educational opportunities, providing free online courses and enhancing digital literacy. Nepal can similarly enhance educational access and quality by developing digital learning platforms and improving internet connectivity in remote areas. China's "Internet Plus" initiative and the "12345" hotline have streamlined government services and improved efficiency. India's Aadhaar project, with its unique identification numbers, has transformed service delivery, increasing transparency and reducing corruption. Nepal can enhance transparency, reduce corruption, and improve service access by implementing e-governance frameworks and digital identity systems. In China, Alibaba's rural e-commerce initiative and government-supported tech parks have revitalized rural economies and supported small businesses, driving overall economic growth (Government of China, 2021). In India, initiatives like Digital India and Start-up India, along with platforms like UPI, have created a vibrant start-up ecosystem and promoted financial inclusion. Nepal can stimulate economic growth and create job opportunities by fostering a conducive environment for start-ups, encouraging digital entrepreneurship, and developing digital payment infrastructure. China's "Internet Hospital" model provides online consultations, medical records access, and prescriptions, improving healthcare access and easing pressure on urban hospitals. India's e-Sanjeevani telemedicine service offers online consultations, expanding healthcare access and reducing the need for physical visits, especially during pandemics. Nepal can enhance healthcare access and timeliness in remote areas by adopting similar telemedicine solutions (Mishra & Jha, 2023). By integrating ICT into agriculture, Nepal can enhance market access, provide valuable information and advisory services, improve supply chain efficiency, and promote financial inclusion (Mishra, 2024). Learning from the experiences of countries like China and India, Nepal can adopt and adapt these technologies to their context, empowering farmers, boosting productivity, and driving socio-economic development in the agricultural sector. Nepal can enhance its tourism sector by leveraging ICT through digital marketing, user-friendly online booking systems, and secure payment gateways. Developing mobile apps with multilingual support and creating virtual reality (VR) tours and augmented reality (AR) guides can improve information accessibility and enrich the tourist experience. These initiatives can attract more international tourists, reduce costs, and boost local business revenue (Mishra & Nepal, 2022).

In conclusion, the potential of ICT to empower the Nepalese community is immense, offering avenues for access to information, connectivity, and education. By effectively implementing ICT initiatives and addressing existing challenges, Nepal can harness the power of technology to drive social and economic development, ultimately fostering a more inclusive and empowered society. As Nepal continues on its digital transformation journey, it is crucial to prioritize efforts that promote digital literacy, expand ICT infrastructure, and ensure equitable access to technology for all members of the community.

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